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1. Introduction

This document describes the emerging biogas communities in the three targeted ISABEL regions, Baden-Württemberg in Germany, Central and Eastern Macedonia and Thrace in Greece and Yorkshire, Lincolnshire and the Humber in UK. Similarly to community energy initiatives, a community biogas can be defined as a biogas project where communities (of place or interest) exhibit a high degree of ownership and control, as well as benefiting collectively from the outcomes¹.

Each potential biogas community is firstly described in terms of its context and geographical characteristics. The main stakeholders are identified and characterized regarding their influence and interest in the formation of a biogas community. Intangible assets such as stakeholder trust and confidence, tacit knowledge, social capital are taken into account, together with tangible assets such as existing biogas plants and other infrastructure, land, access to feedstocks and biowaste, financial asset that could be conducive to the creation of a biogas community.

Then, for each community the stakeholder engagement strategy and community building activities are described, considering the key messages for the engagement and the stage of the social innovation (SI) sequence, introduced and described in the ISABEL deliverable D 1.4 (see Figure 1). Potential SI animators have been identified in certain communities; these are individuals or organizations among the targeted stakeholders that have shown motivation and skills in further mobilizing local actors and coordinating the foreseen activities, maintaining cohesion and direction in the emerging community.

Through the engagement and community building activities (such as workshops and info-days), each emerging community and stakeholder platform started to develop their own vision for a biogas community. This vision contains various dimensions, such as: the value proposition of the community, that is the innovation and feature that most attract the stakeholders in joining the biogas community; the structural elements such as feedstock, digestate and energy flows related to the foreseen biogas system, and its size and scale; the organizational structure which will coordinate relations and actions of the stakeholders.

As the community building is an ongoing process happening along the whole ISABEL project, also its next planned steps are included, together with potential challenges and opportunities, to give a long term perspective and integrating lessons learnt from past activities.

Figure 1. Social innovation progress as introduced in the ISABEL deliverable D 1.4

¹ Walker, G., & Devine-Wright, P. (2008). Community renewable energy: What should it mean? *Energy Policy*, 36(2), 497–500. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2007.10.019>

2. Biogas communities in Germany

2.1 Obereschach biogas community

2.1.1 Description of the community

Obereschach is a borough of the district capital Villingen-Schwenningen (VS) in the Schwarzwald-Baar district, located about 8km away from the district capital. Obereschach lies in the Black Forest, about 760m above sea level, it is characterized by strong winters and has an annual average temperature of about 7 C.

Obereschach was once a rural village with many farms. Since the incorporation as borough to VS in the year 1971 it became attractive for persons who work in VS while wishing to have a house in the countryside. Infrastructure (schools, public transport) helped to develop the village and the number of inhabitants raised from 1.000 in 1970 to 1.700 today. Most of the inhabitants lives in family houses with large gardens. Agriculture reforms and a change towards an industrial and service oriented society had the consequence that many traditional farms declined.

Biogas production plays an important role in the farming sector in Obereschach. Three biogas plants are currently located in Obereschach:

- Mosbacher – 170 kWe
- Zimmermann – 75 kWe
- Bußhart – 230 kWe

Figure 2. Map of the Obereschach village, with indicated the three local biogas plants.

The Bußhart biogas plant lies 500 m from the village boundaries of Obereschach. The operator contacted LCF and expressed his wish to cooperate. The biogas plant operates since 2004.

After interviewing the biogas operator, Mr. Bußhart, LCF decided to set a first biogas community in Obereschach. The criteria for the choice were:

- Openness and willingness to collaborate from the biogas operator.
- A requirement to improve the current operation of the biogas plant.
- Need of finding an alternative to revenues from electricity feed-in-tariff, whose support for the plant is ending in the next years.

The main feedstocks are energy crops such as maize silage, and manure. In particular, the use of maize has reduced the acceptance of the biogas plants by the local population. However, the use of available waste materials such as green cuts and organic waste, more socially acceptable, faces legal and organizational barriers.

Because of the urban structure in Obereschach and the large garden areas around each house, there is a certain potential of biomass and organic waste for the biogas production out of each garden. Despite a typical

demographic change in rural areas, the predictions in Obereschach prognosticate a stable evolution of the population. Also the average household size in Obereschach is higher than the rest of the district city in Villingen-Schwenningen. The existing biogas plant is technically up to date and regularly maintained by the farmer. The other two surrounding biogas plants offer the potential to develop the community biogas initiative at a larger scale.

While the knowledge level of biogas is quite high among the local population, there is less awareness and consensus regarding the possible alternatives in the operation and output products. A co-creation process and new participation models, with broader citizen involvement, is seen as instrumental to identify options for a future production and utilization of biogas that is resource efficient, climate friendly, economically feasible and with high benefits for the community.

In this regard, an analysis of the geographical context and a search of relevant stakeholders were the first actions carried out by the regional ISABEL partner. Five groups of stakeholders have been identified as key to re-design the operation of the biogas plant and lead towards a new biogas community:

- Biogas plant operators
- Public authorities
- General public, village citizens
- Regional energy suppliers
- National authorities and politics

Being a small village, the local stakeholders know each other quite well and are used to work and talk together. While there are some diverging views about nature conservation and regional development across the different stakeholder groups (e.g. biogas plant owners and citizens), there is nevertheless a goodwill to cooperate with each other.

The village council and the mayor support the idea to develop a community based biogas project, and as such this aspect constitutes one of the main intangible assets of the emerging community.

The local biogas operator already tried to find different ways how to sensitize the citizens for biogas and tried different flowering crops near the village as alternative feedstock. A first initiative to implement a district heating wasn't successful in the past because of a lack of time to develop the project.

2.1.2 Methodology of engagement and community building

As described above, different stakeholder groups were identified. The overall focus of the engagement was on the generation of new ideas and propositions for the use of biogas. The stakeholder engagement has been focused on three local groups: the biogas plant owners, the local authorities and the village citizens, with an aim to generate interest for a community biogas. The ISABEL regional partner chose the following strategy:

- A systematic research of relevant persons with a newspaper and online desktop research to identify potential multipliers in the village.
- A **preliminary presentation of the project** in the village council, where the purpose and the potential opportunities for the village were described. The presentation was tailored to open up the various possibilities available and to avoid a pre-fixed idea of the project and of the process.
- Following the preliminary presentation, a **co-creation workshop was organized**, where the main stakeholders were invited. The following steps were carried out:
 - a. Send personal invitations and information to all members of the village council. The members of the council are traditionally the first to be asked for further information. All information needed to be correct and precise to avoid misunderstandings and wrong expectations of the project.
 - b. After informing the village council, LCF sent an invitation to the main associations like football clubs, fire brigade, and nature conservation organizations by email.

- c. After the first feedback and registration LCF decided to phone all members of the village council and the board of the clubs to convince them to attend. LCF used the phone calls for further explanations on the detailed purpose of the workshop and why it is important to attend.
- d. In parallel to the phone calls, an announcement appeared in the local community newspaper that is delivered to all households in Obereschach. With the announcement LCF tried to reinforce the exchange process between the citizens.
- e. For further and more detailed information a notice was published on the LCF homepage and a reference to the ISABEL homepage.
- f. The ISABEL project flyer was distributed to the participants of the workshop.

The workshop took place at the village council, with the participation of 5 members of the village council, 3 biogas plant owners and 4 citizens from the village. Noticeably, the participants were mostly elderly and male people. The influence of the participants in the village can be considered as high because half of the council members participated. The workshop had also the support of the mayor who couldn't attend but excused himself.

The workshop included an introduction of the ISABEL project followed by a brainstorming exercise with the key questions: a) what is your association/perception of biogas? b) How can biogas be integrated into the community? The contributions from the attendees were then clustered into three different groups:

- Related to the biogas plant, which included suggestions for feedstock inputs, operating time, smell, traffic.
- Related to forms of participation to a potential biogas community: financial, provision of feedstock materials, and use of products (gas, electricity, heat/refrigeration, fertilizer).
- Related to potential development at a regional and infrastructural level, including: gas station, gas network, electricity network, district heating network, waste management, integration with other renewable energies.

Each contribution was then assessed by the participants, who scored their favorite contribution through adhesive points.

Overall, the workshop was very productive and made the community more aware of the available options and increased their sense of responsibility in the co-creation of regional development. Both the biogas plant owners and the members of the town council were supportive of a community based solution for the use of biogas energy. As such, the engagement process covers the **awareness to evaluation step** in the sequential approach to social innovation (see deliverable of ISABEL D 1.4, p. 31).

The village council and the mayor play a key role in approaching the citizens. Only with the support of these two communal organs further actions can take place in the village. This supports the experience LCF already made working with smaller villages. The institutions need to be convinced by the importance of the project and the advantages that can be delivered for the community.

Rural citizens are very aware of "common" biogas practices like combined heat and power, but have problems to think freely and to be innovative. It is helpful to refer to best practice communities nearby.

It is a certain opportunity to already have existing know-how about biogas when trying to create interest for the participation in concrete projects. However, it is a known challenge in community projects to maintain cohesion and interest in the initial engagement period with a high amount of volunteering time and when the project vision and management is still emerging and unsure.

Next steps of engagement will include:

- Workshop evaluation by participants.
- Online survey to involve a broader base of the village population.
- Excursion to a bioenergy village to show a best practice.

- Second workshop / meeting with additional information presented by LCF, including the results of the online survey.
- Collect additional information on the main topics (e.g. heat utilization and available residues/wastes).
- Match visions and scenarios from the workshop with possibilities of existing biogas plants

Other regional public authorities will also be engaged in the next steps. For a wider perception of the project, surrounding public authorities will need to be engaged. They can offer a different perception of the possible projects in the village, and are required in the planning phase. A strong alliance between the biogas plant owners and the nearby farmers may help to develop the project at a larger scale and will facilitate the identification of available biomass and waste potentials. Support from regional nature conservation organizations may help to avoid critical comments on a biogas project.

Figure 3. Stakeholders workshop in Obereschach.

Figure 4. Results from the brainstorm exercise.

Figure 5. Topics scored by the participants.

2.1.3 Emerging community structure and vision

A detailed vision for the community biogas is still emerging. However, following the discussion and scoring step of the workshop, three topics appeared most important towards the formation of a sustainable biogas community:

- Fully use the heat potential for district heating. Local public buildings, which are usual anchor users for district heating, were recently equipped with new wood pellet burners. This is a potential barrier; however, district heating could provide peak supply. A biogas district heating system could lead to a long term reduction of heating costs. At the moment however, low price of fossil fuels makes hard the comparison on a purely monetary basis. This is one reason of the difficulty in realizing heating projects at the moment.
- The increased use of waste materials as a feedstock. New resources to substitute expensive feedstocks (such as maize silage) need to be used in order to produce biogas with a lower cost. At the same time a re-organization of the current local waste management will be needed.
- The integration of a potential community biogas initiative in a wider energy transition for the whole community, leading to higher degree of energy self-sufficiency and considering the contribution of other renewable and demand side management.

Overall, there was consensus towards a regional development with renewable energy and supporting the community to create new value chains. The importance of environmental protection and an increase of biodiversity is not opposite to a sustainable production of biogas.

In order to maintain current infrastructure like local biogas plants that do not receive fixed feed-in tariffs any more, financial participation and stronger involvement of citizens can be a solution. The re-design of the waste management and the citizen contribution in running the biogas plant through garden waste can improve as well the community cohesion.

The wider, systemic services that a biogas plant can provide, such as in landscape management, can have a certain benefit for the village to preserve the multifaceted surroundings and to be attractive for tourism.

A community biogas initiative will integrate an already existing energy infrastructure. Considering a local photovoltaic system and the three surrounding biogas plants, 150% of the required electrical power of the

village is produced locally. Using the waste heat from the three biogas plants, 50% of the heating requirements of the village could be satisfied.

The organisation of the biogas community will be facilitated by LCF during the initial stages, with a view to promote a self-organisation of the community in later stages. Therefore, regular meetings and points of information have to be determined. It is helpful that existing structures like the municipal institutions are informed and involved. A further formalization will probably be developed at a later stage. Communication in the community may be diverse ranging from mobile applications, e-mail, telephone and local newspaper to announcements table or informal meetings at the local bakery.

At the actual stage there is no legal organization form required. All milestones (create more awareness, sensitize, acceptance and potential overview) can be reached without the need of a legal organization form.

The main challenges ahead consist in ensuring a broader citizen participation, and solve the legal barriers that currently restricts the feeding of waste materials in farm based biogas plants.

Schwarzwälder Bote

Villingen-Schwenningen

Dialog mit Bürgern

Von Schwarzwälder-Bote 03.12.2016 - 02:15 Uhr

In einem Bürgerdialog informierte Volker Kromrey (links) von der Bodensee-Stiftung interessierte Oberschacher Bürger über die unterschiedliche Nutzung von Biogas. Foto: Weiß Foto: Schwarzwälder-Bote

VS-Obereschach (we). Zwölf Interessenten hatten sich zu einem ersten Bürgerdialog mit der Bodensee-Stiftung, einer internationalen Stiftung für Natur und Kultur, im Vereinsheim "Alte Schule" eingefunden, um sich über ein EU-gefördertes Biogasprojekt informieren zu lassen.

Wie Volker Kromrey, Dimitri Vedel, Matthias Koppe und Antje Föll von der Bodensee-Stiftung darlegten, wollen sie verschiedenen Akteuren aus dem Ort die Möglichkeit bieten, zusammen zu kommen und die regionale Entwicklung mitzugestalten. Die Stiftung ist bereits in den Landkreisen Tuttlingen und Sigmaringen erfolgreich im Einsatz, um Gemeinschaften mit ihrem Fachwissen und ihrer Beratung zu Biogas und gemeinschaftliche Energieprojekte zu unterstützen.

Figure 6. Press release after the workshop, to further engage the local population.

3. Biogas Communities in Greece

3.1 “NEOGAL” Biogas community

3.1.1 Description of the community

The **Cooperative Dairy NEOGAL** (<http://neogal.gr>) is located in the Drama County (Central Macedonia – North Greece). Its activities cover the collection, processing and selling of cow, goat and sheep milk in the local and national market. It was founded in 1964 by the Union of Dairy Cooperatives of Drama/Kavalla Counties (40% of shares) and the Agricultural Bank of Greece (60% of shares). Since 1997 the company opened its capital to shares from its employees and regional milk producers.

Currently, NEOGAL is run by a Boarding Council which is elected by the shareholders General Assembly. It is a financially stable company and its product portfolio includes a wide range of dairy products (i.e. several types of milk, cheese, yogurt and ice-cream) which are sold in major cities and areas of Greece (e.g. Central and Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, Thessaloniki, Attica-Athens) and abroad (e.g. Italy and Germany).

The company constantly invests in the modernization of infrastructure of livestock breeders, such as technological solutions for milk production and processing, in order to improve productivity and quality, with the aim of expanding its business and distribution network.

Figure 7. Drama county, region of Eastern Macedonia

3.1.2 Methodology of engagement and community building

The initial stakeholders that have been contacted are the members of the board as well as other key personnel of the cooperative dairy industry NEOGAL; this allowed in turn getting in contact with livestock breeders and dairy employees, members of the cooperative.

Greek ISABEL partners used their network with dairy industries which resulted into a first, face-to-face meeting with NEOGAL board members, including the board president in mid October 2016. The intent was of raising their interest in the ISABEL activities and presenting the general benefits of biogas. This first meeting corresponds to the **unawareness to awareness step** of the sequential approach to social innovation.

The following step corresponded to the **awareness to evaluation step** on the social innovation progress. A round table took place in early December 2016, at NEOGAL’s headquarters, with the participation of board members, sales department personnel dairy employees and livestock breeders. The key messages included:

- the environmental, social and financial benefits of biogas initiatives for the local community and NEOGAL cooperative.
- The ability to tackle with legislation obligations on livestock waste treatment.

- The contribution of NEOGAL to low carbon activities and the enhancement of its environmental profile.

Furthermore, an introductory presentation was made on structural, operational and financial issues concerning a potential biogas plant initiative. Through a comprehensive discussion with stakeholders, ISABEL made an agenda of issues that should be discussed in more detail in future engagement events.

ISABEL partners identified key “**social innovation animators**” among board members, especially the President of the board who is a livestock breeder as well. The social innovation animator acts as the champion of the emerging community, supporting the community vision through further stakeholder mobilisation and coordination. The president showed great enthusiasm and acceptance to the biogas plant community initiative and supported the communication of ISABEL concept to the other members of the NEOGAL cooperative. ISABEL partners will collaborate closely with his leadership to facilitate NEOGAL biogas community’s action plan.

Additionally, it was proposed that in the future with ISABEL support, NEOGAL will contact other stakeholders, basically from local communities, to participate in the emerging biogas community and enhance with their presence the implementation of a potential biogas plant. The stakeholders that are expected to be contacted are:

- Dairy industries
- Public authorities at local and national level
- Members of environmental NGOs
- Owners of local greenhouse businesses
- Any other stakeholder that could be an asset for NEOGAL biogas community (e.g., policy makers)

3.1.3 Emerging community structure and vision

The perspective of a biogas community is consonant with the long term vision of NEOGAL of supporting its members and local stakeholders towards a sustainable future, financial and environmentally:

- Innovate its industrial infrastructure, including a reduction in energy consumption.
- Introduce local breeders to best practices, including legally and environmentally appropriate livestock and dairy waste management procedures.
- Achieve higher quality for its products.
- Supply its products to major cities and areas of Greece (e.g. Central and Eastern Macedonia and Thrace, Thessaloniki, Attica-Athens) and facilitate the further expansion in EU market (e.g. Italy and Germany).

In this regard, a community biogas plant is considered as strategically important, as it would lead to the following advantages:

- An effective compliance of livestock breeders to waste management legislation. Currently and in some cases, the storage and treatment procedures don’t fully comply with the waste management legislation (e.g. there is no appropriate liquid waste treatment infrastructure).
- The production of renewable energy, mainly cogeneration of heat and electricity via CHP from biogas. Electricity would be exported to the grid, while heat would be sold to neighbouring greenhouses. Furthermore, a part of the produced biogas would be transported through suitable infrastructure to dairy industrial facilities or neighbouring settlements for heating.
- The use of digestate as organic fertiliser, to be distributed to NEOGAL members’ farms, improving the current practice of using manure and chemical fertilizers.
- In general, it would reduce the environmental footprint of NEOGAL and its members and produce new revenues in the form of feed-in-tariff from electricity, heat exploitation and decreased costs for fertilisers.

The emerging biogas community will unite an initial cluster of livestock breeders from the current NEOGAL members. The biogas plant would treat manure, crops residues and dairy wastes, and the produced digestate would be re-distributed to nearby farmers. Additionally, the produced heat could be sold to neighbouring greenhouses. The identification of the cluster will require the following:

- Identifying an ideal site and size for the biogas plant, which will depend on the relative abundance of feedstock, land availability and energy (heat) demand.
- Ideate an organizational method for sharing the benefits and revenues from the operation of the biogas plants amongst the cluster participants and the remaining members of the cooperative.

A successful clustering and organizational scheme will therefore be one of the main outcomes of the ISABEL initiative, which could then be scaled out amongst the other members of the NEOGAL cooperative and also in other similar cooperatives in Greece.

3.2 Leda Maria biogas community

3.2.1 Description of the community

Leda Maria settlement is a suburban area of Thermi Municipality, next to the urban agglomeration of Thessaloniki (Thessaloniki county). Offices and 150 families share the management of the communal area, including surveillance, maintenance of electrical infrastructure, garden and household waste disposal.

A Community Administrative Council is annually elected and is responsible for the operation and management of the Leda Maria settlement, while block of apartments administrators provide their collaboration to the community's management and internal communication procedures. The Leda Maria inhabitants have a general meeting on a semester basis where all the aspects and plans are discussed and decisions are made.

The ambition of the community is to become more sustainable in their practices, and aim to establish a community energy organization which could renegotiate current contracts with energy suppliers and explore on-site renewable energy generation.

Figure 8. Thessaloniki county, region of Central Macedonia.

Figure 9. Leda Maria settlement, urban agglomeration of Thessaloniki.

3.2.2 *Methodology of engagement and community building*

The stakeholders that have been contacted so far are the administrative council members and individual inhabitants of the Leda Maria settlement.

Greek ISABEL partners had a first meeting with the former president of the administrative council. This event served to present the concept of establishing an energy community for Leda Maria as a promising scheme to provide low cost and environmentally friendly energy supply to the settlement. As such, it played the role of **unawareness to awareness step** on the social innovation progress. After this first event, the president of the council presented the concept to the rest of the administrative council. Given the interest from the members, the ISABEL partners gave another presentation to the council during their annual general meeting, in November. The concept was well accepted by all members.

As a next step, ISABEL partners distributed a brochure to the mailboxes of all inhabitants of the settlement, explaining the vision and the benefits of setting up a biogas energy community. They also made a presentation to the inhabitants during the Leda Maria general meeting (December), where a major part of them was present. The key messages that were presented included:

- The possibility of re-negotiating current contracts with electricity providers and requesting a higher share of renewable electricity in their supply mix.
- The ability to promote sustainable energy consumption and production methods that lead to low carbon economy.
- The potential of a biogas plant in Leda Maria, with the use of electricity and heat generated for Leda Maria settlement demands.
- The investigation of potential synergies with nearby communities in the establishment of a community biogas plant initiative, such as the use of household waste from all communities to feed the biogas plant and potential co-investment and sharing of electricity production revenues.

Furthermore, an introductory presentation was made on structural, financial and feedstock mix issues concerning the potential of micro biogas plant initiative. This presentation corresponds to the **awareness to evaluation step** on social innovation progress.

The former president of the Administrative Council is willing to provide his full support in the communication among ISABEL and the community. For instance he has established a productive collaboration among ISABEL partners and a current Administrative Council member, responsible for communicating for ISABEL issues.

In the immediate future, Leda Maria Biogas Community Energy plans to engage several other stakeholders, that can potentially contribute to the Community's goals, namely:

- neighbouring settlements.
- Neighbouring office blocks.
- Neighbouring shopping malls.
- Neighbouring university faculties.
- Environmental NGOs members.
- Public authorities at local and national level.

Figure 10. ISABEL presentation at the general assembly of Leda Maria settlement, 11th December 2016.

3.2.3 Emerging community structure and vision

Leda Maria Biogas Energy Community will be established as a **no-profit association** by the members of the local community. The main ambitions of the association are the following:

- To exert pressure on the existing national energy suppliers by collectively renegotiate the current energy contracts for the whole settlement and investigate available options for an increased share of renewables in their energy mix, including supply from photovoltaic, wind and biogas systems.
- To promote and plan a community biogas initiative among the settlement members and neighbouring communities (e.g. other settlements and university faculties) and explore the possibility of a district heating solution.

The community biogas initiative would be technically enabled by a micro biogas unit/plant, which would be fed by the food waste and garden waste from the settlement and potentially nearby communities. The biogas produced would be used to cover part of the community's electrical and heating demands or would provide extra revenue to all collaborative communities' members (electricity insert to the grid). The produced digestate would be used for in communal gardening areas. From a social point of view, a strong engagement from all settlement inhabitants will be promoted. A nearby farm school could play a role in developing another biogas unit and exploring the possibility of a district heating grid.

Overall, the Leda Maria Biogas Community Energy aspires to become a role model for other local communities in terms of recognising their potentials in achieving a safe, reliable, environmentally friendly and low cost energy supply. A successful scheme could be shared and replicated with other communities in Greece.

3.3 Prespes biogas community

3.3.1 Description of the Community

The community will be located in the Municipality of Prespa. This place has unique characteristics for forming a biogas energy community. Of particular importance is the environmentally vulnerable region of the Prespa Lake Basin, home to more than 2,000 species of fish, birds, mammals and plants, which has suffered environmental pressure over the last 40 years — above all from pollution caused by unsustainable farming practices, together with erosion and the presence of untreated waste and wastewaters. As a consequence, the high eutrophic condition of the lakes leads to an excessive growth of biomass, particularly reeds, that endangers the endemic species.

Two main stakeholders have been identified initially by the regional ISABEL partners: the Society for the Protection of Prespa and the management body of Prespa National Park. They share a common vision for the environmental protection of the lakes located in the national park, with a focus on controlling livestock wastes from animal farming and the fertilizers that farmers use on their lands. Their plan is to mobilize the farmers to form a biogas energy community to enable the environmental treatment of manure through a biogas plant and reduce the run-off of nutrients into the lakes.

During summer time, a large part of livestock migrates to the pastures. Therefore, in this period another source of substrate to feed the biogas plant will be needed. This operational challenge is addressed by considering the invasive reeds from the lake as a feedstock for biogas production. In this way, another environmental issue of the national park is handled in an environmental and legally effective way. Generally, it is expected that the improved manure management through the biogas plant will help in keeping the lake eutrophication under control. The amount of reeds that is cut every year is available from a previous LIFE project in which the Society for the Protection of Prespa was involved.

Overall, the emerging biogas community will include the following stakeholders:

- the Society for the Protection of Prespa, <http://www.spp.gr/>
- The Management Body of Prespa National Park, <http://www.fdedp.gr>
- The members of the Livestock Association of Municipality of Prespa.
- The Municipality of Prespa.
- The agricultural cooperative of bean producers "PELICAN", <http://www.prespabeans.gr/>

Figure 11. Florina county, region of Western Macedonia.

Figure 12. Prespes area, North West Greece, borders with Albania and FYROM.

3.3.2 Methodology of engagement and community building

ISABEL partners had some initial contacts with members of local authorities and associations, namely:

- An active ecologist, who is a scientific associate of the Municipality of Prespes.
- A representative of the Society for the Protection of Prespa.
- The president of the Livestock association of the Municipality of Prespa.
- The president of the Agricultural Cooperative of Bean Producers "PELICAN".

They all agreed that measures should be implemented for the protection of the natural environment of the area. One of the principal objectives of the two organizations (Society for the Protection of Prespa and The

Management Body of Prespa National Park) together with the Municipality of Prespa is to stop the uncontrolled management of manure and to implement legal and effective management of the excessive biomass (reeds) growth.

The stakeholder engagement process is still in the first phase. The support of ISABEL partners in the development of the PRESIPA biogas community is planned to include these following engagement and community building steps:

Step 1: From Unawareness Stage to Awareness Stage – Setting up the biogas Community

Hold a kick-off meeting to:

- outline the project idea, to consult on local community needs, to foster the local cooperation between partners, and to prepare together with all the stakeholders the future actions.
- To actively integrate the whole supply network. There will be a discussion to realize synergies and for meeting the needs of all the supply chain actors. A wide discussion with the involvement of all the stakeholders will allow to identify:
 - o the shared values
 - o the community needs
 - o the potential conflicts
 - o the common problems and interests
 - o any regional development patterns
 - o the habits and life styles and the past activities.
- Estimate support and potential volunteers within the community (social feasibility).
- Process and timescale for consultation on preferred options.
- Present best practice examples and references.

Step 2: From Awareness Stage to Evaluation Stage

- An organizational structure will be established, for monitoring the biogas energy community operation.
- Get available data from the main five stakeholders. The data will cover the agricultural by-products potentials and the spatial description of agricultural by-products potentials, including the quantity of reeds being cut during a year, data about the quantity and quality of manure in the area, the geographical location of livestock, the geographical location of reeds, the hectares of beans and potatoes cultivated in the area, the average yield, etc. The quality of reeds will be tested for anaerobic digestion experiments in a laboratory.
- Develop scenarios for different suitable supply chain management and co-ordination issues.
- Develop a technical and financial feasibility study.
- Develop a business plan.
- Hold an open meeting to:
 - o Report findings from assessment and feasibility studies.
 - o Report findings from feasibility study.
 - o Report findings from business plan.
 - o Discuss all scenarios.
 - o Agree preferred scenario.

- Agree process and timescale for consultation on preferred scenario.
- Address any outstanding issues.
- Get into contact with other similar biogas energy communities for exchanging know-how and for seeing up-close the way they operate, their profits, the problems encountered and the way they solved them, and finally their thoughts and plans for the future.
- Hold a meeting to confirm the feedstock commitment from the supply chain providers and sign a Memorandum of Understanding.

3.3.3 Emerging community structure and vision

Prespa area is a border area of the country with great national, geo-strategic, environmental and cultural value. In general the area has low income. The main economic activities are fishing, agriculture, livestock and tourism. The lakes constitute the centre of activities.

Essential prerequisite for the sustainability of lakes is to address the phenomenon of eutrophication. Eutrophication is the result of agricultural and livestock activity in the area around the lakes. Farmers use fertilizers on their fields which are then partially drained into the lakes. The manure, that comes from cows bred in the area, pollutes the soils and also by extension the lake.

However, organizations with great experience and substantial interest in the lakes' issues are operating in the area for many years. These organizations are the Society for the Protection of Prespa and the Agricultural Cooperative of Bean Producers "PELICAN". These could be the main stakeholders for the establishment and operation of Prespa's biogas energy community. They recognize the critical state of the fragile, vulnerable, and strikingly beautiful ecosystem. They seek to convince inhabitants of the need to insure healthy lakes as a primary source, and as sources of food and economic livelihoods, utilizing them in a manner that maximizes their sustainable use for humans and nature, while also preserving their quality and ecosystem integrity for current and future generations.

The inhabitants need to manage the area resources in an integrated manner in order to facilitate their sustainability. This involves:

- A future in which inhabitants manage and use the lakes and their resources with the guiding view of preserving and improving them, rather than presiding over their continuing degradation.
- A future in which the understanding of lakes includes recognition of their inseparable connections to the drainage basins that surround and nourish them, and to the people whose activities control lakes' health and vitality.
- A future in which the importance of water from clean lakes is recognized as a life and death issue for the economy of the area.
- A future in which environmental protection of the lakes is initiated and pursued in a coordinated manner that increases human knowledge of their properties and functions, and benefits effective policy formation and management practices identified as important to the health and sustainable use of Lake Basin ecosystems.

These two bodies will be the leaders for establishing the biogas community in the area. They will invite the Livestock association of Municipality of Prespa, the Management Body of Prespa National Park and the Municipality of Prespa, to support and promote this vision for the future.

ISABEL partners and the two bodies will support the establishment of Prespa's biogas energy community. The potential biogas plant will:

- Use a mixture of the manure from the livestock and the reeds from the lake.
- The thermal energy that will be produced will be used either to a district heating system for houses in the area or in a productive process (cannery, green house, etc).

- The digestate that will be produced by the potential biogas plant will be an improved organic fertilizer for the farmers, with a reduced risk of nitrate run-offs.

The benefits of forming a biogas energy community and establishing a biogas plant are:

- Preservation and protection of the two lakes that are the most significant source of wealth for the region.
- Manure management in a legal and prosperous way.
- Sustainable and profitable management of the cut reeds of the lakes.
- Free organic fertilizer, ideal for the agriculture activities, especially for the organic ones
- Significant revenue from the sale of the electricity
- Significant reduce of air pollution through the implementation of district heating to heat houses and/or municipal buildings
- The region will retain the tourist character as there will be preservation of the unique beauty of the lakes.
- Finally, all these economic benefits in the area could revitalize the local economy.

4. Biogas communities in UK

4.1 Hockerton biogas community

4.1.1 Description of the Community

The core of the emerging biogas community is Hockerton, a village and civil parish at the border between Lincolnshire and Nottinghamshire. There are 60 households and a population of 150 inhabitants.

Figure 13. Hockerton village and the initial stakeholder Hockerton housing project

The initial stakeholders and entry point for ISABEL have been the Hockerton Housing Project and Sustainable Hockerton. These are the key stakeholders, as they have already experience with community energy projects, and a network of contacts with other local key actors.

Hockerton Housing Project is a community business and a self-sufficient co-housing development. They built one of the first examples in the UK of earth sheltered, self-sufficient ecological housing development, with reduced heating requirements, local food production (vegetable gardens, polytunnels, aquaponics) and wastewater treatment. They also run a not-for-profit co-operative which hosts tours and courses for all ages, and provides consultancy services to help others deliver sustainability at home, community or workplace levels.

Sustainable Hockerton is an Industrial and Provident Society (IPS) formed by a group of Hockerton residents in 2009. The aim of Sustainable Hockerton is to make Hockerton a more sustainable village and reduce the amount of carbon released into the atmosphere. The Society has installed a 225 kW wind turbine and 87 kW solar PV, which generates income from feed in tariffs. Any financial surplus is distributed to the parish to promote sustainable development projects (such as building retrofits and other efficiency measures).

Other stakeholders that have been contacted by ISABEL and will collaborate in the development of the biogas community are:

- The parish council. It is responsible for planning application, access and use of public buildings and assets, allocation of allotments for community gardens, provision and maintenance of recreation grounds, parks, playing fields and roadside verges.
- Woodside Farm, a local farm in Hockerton, which aims to improve the sustainability of its activities. It is family run farm with 3 chicken sheds (approx. 60,000 chickens in total), cattle sheds and arable, grazing land as well as grain stores
- The local pub in Hockerton, which could act as a “**social innovation animator**”.

- Nottingham Trent University, School of Animal Rural & Environmental Sciences. Students can be involved in surveys with the village population, in feasibility studies and other locally based research, both experimental or desk based.
- A local newspaper, the “Newark Advertiser”, which helps in promoting the ISABEL activities and raise awareness of the local population about biogas.
- British Sugar, which operates a large factory in Newark, 10 km away. Corporate social responsibility could provide funds for infrastructure spending. They have experience in AD and other bioprocesses to valorize biowastes.

Figure 14 Wind turbine installed by Sustainable Hockerton (left) and detail of the Hockerton Housing Project (right) (Images: Hockerton Housing Co-operative)

Biogas explained

A COMMUNITY group is running a free workshop about the benefits of biogas energy production.

Members of Isabel, a community biogas project in the Hockerton area, are hosting the event at Hockerton Housing Project’s centre in Gables Drive on Saturday.

Biogas energy production involves the digestion of organic material by organisms under anaerobic conditions to create gas containing methane, as a source of energy, and nutrients for growing food crops.

Davide Poggio, workshop organiser, said: “We will be exploring together with the local community the potential for a community biogas in Hockerton.”

Isabel is an EU-funded project, involving a team from Global

Biotechnology Transfer Foundation, in Lincolnshire, who are working with the University of Surrey’s Centre for Research in Social Simulation (CRESS).

Simon Tilley, of Hockerton Housing Project, said: “Benefits of community biogas include a storable renewable fuel, healthy rich compost suitable for food production and a use for organic waste.”

Saturday’s workshops run from 11am until 1pm. Lunch is provided.

To book a place email contact@hockertonhousingproject.org.uk

There will also be tour of the Hockerton Housing Project from 2pm till 5pm. To book visit www.hockertonhousingproject.org.uk

● **ECO-HOME PLAN REJECTED:**
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Figure 15 Workshop advertisement published on the “Newark Advertiser”, November 10th, 2016

4.1.2 *Methodology of engagement and community building*

The initial contacts were with Hockerton Housing Project and Sustainable Hockerton, as they were seen as role models of community groups and as offering a fertile ground for testing new approaches to community biogas. Initial personal contacts with the director of Sustainable Hockerton confirmed their interest in exploring biogas as solution to local biowaste valorization.

An initial presentation of the ISABEL project was given during the Annual General Meeting with the board of directors and members of Sustainable Hockerton. This presentation had the objective to introduce the key stakeholders to the ISABEL project and verify together the desirability of a possible collaboration.

The focus of the presentation was the vision of ISABEL as a platform for connecting local initiatives and promoting sharing and learning in order to co-design innovative solutions for sustainable communities. An overview was also given of the possible technical solutions which enable the local treatment of biowaste and the production of energy and food. In particular, an initial scenario of community biogas for the village was described, including: the treatment of the food waste produced in the village (60 households), and the recycling of nutrients (digestate) into a polytunnel heated by biogas with increased food production (vegetables and mushrooms) to be locally distributed. The presentation was well received and led to a question and answer session:

- how to promote the collaboration between all the actors (e.g. village households, local businesses, local authorities)?
 - o It is one of the objectives of ISABEL to explore new business and organizational models for community biogas. There are no established blueprints available; rather, a social innovation approach will enable new solutions to emerge.
- How to reconcile the desire of the community to reduce the amount of food waste, with the requirements to operate the biogas plant?
 - o The system should be designed taking into account a reduction of available food waste during its operation, and therefore using other sources of waste (animal or agro waste) available. Reducing food waste produced could be included as one of the monitoring and evaluation indicators by the community.
- How to finance the project?
 - o Sustainable Hockerton has incomes in the form of feed in tariffs from other renewable technologies (PV and wind), which could be used to finance the construction and operation of the community biogas. It could be an interesting cross-subsidizing scheme across a community business. Main incomes of the community biogas would be from the production of vegetable and mushrooms, rather than from the energy generated.

Following this initial meeting, a follow-up workshop was organized and further stakeholder engagement was carried out to include other actors of the community. Contacts with the parish council, local farmers and other interested village citizens were made through members of Sustainable Hockerton at the local village meeting; ISABEL made direct contacts with Nottingham Trent University and British Sugar, and with the general local public through advertisement in a local newspaper. Representatives of the charity Community Lincs, from the other biogas community from Lincoln (see section below), also participated. As the vision of the biogas community is still emerging, it is possible that representatives from other nearby villages will be involved in the next steps of the process.

The participants had mixed backgrounds and knowledge of biogas and community energy, and therefore the presentation and workshop design were tailored to cover both the communication (**unawareness to awareness step on social innovation progress**) and the information dissemination (**awareness to evaluation step**). Therefore, similarly to the first meeting, an initial presentation introduced the participants to the ISABEL project visions and to the main options (technical, organizational, financial) for a community biogas initiative. The second part of the workshop consisted of an envisioning session, where participants were invited to sketch possible biogas community visions, facilitated by a set of “biogas archetypes” cards, showing them different options in terms of inputs, outputs, organizational models and monetary and non-monetary

values. These cards are thought to help the stakeholders to explore the range of options for a community biogas and the alternative values that can be enabled and captured, such as:

- Anaerobic digestion as a link in local food chains, connecting producers and consumers through the recycling of food and domestic waste to production areas. Potential organizational models could come from community supported agriculture experiences, such as veg-box schemes and multi-stakeholder cooperatives. Revenues from the operation of the biogas plants could be redistributed to the food chain stakeholders.
- Anaerobic digestion as a trigger for an improved ecosystem management. In this case the focus would be on ecosystem services such as soil protection and increased biodiversity, using different crops, such as wild flowers, or changing the management of the road and amenity verges.
- Regeneration of unused assets and brownfields, which could lead to new community centers with multiple activities (such as different food production activities), powered by biogas.
- Energy output for local use, such as district heating and vehicle fuels. Those approaches allow a higher control by the community on tariffs, than selling electricity on the national grid. Gas upgrade to biomethane is becoming feasible at small scale.
- Integration of biogas with other renewables. In this case biogas plays the role of storage in a local grid, and would ideally fit into an energy club² or private wire, with pooling of energy generation and demand side management.
- Integration of bioprocesses, with multiple products from local closed loops: vegetables, mushroom, compost, earthworms, aquaponics, fermented beverages, etc. This would result in more value produced and could be developed as could be developed as an energy and nutrient self-sufficient and self-contained infrastructural solution
- Network of small scale digesters operating in a given region, allowing higher flexibility and resilience of the biogas community.
- Opportunity for training, education and outreach, when considering an eco-centre for the demonstration of new opportunities of the circular economy, food production, entrepreneurial skills, etc.

Overall, the second workshop conveyed the co-production and co-design dimension of ISABEL, which links the local perspectives and values together with the external technical and scientific knowledge. In this regard, the co-production process would go through iterative steps of desirable, viable and feasible scenarios of community biogas, with ISABEL facilitating interactions between the local stakeholders and the expert knowledge.

Some relevant challenges and questions were identified and raised by the participants: investments and returns on investments, health and safety, commercial availability of the required equipment, which size and location of the systems, how to implement the collection of waste.

This bottom-up approach is seen as instrumental to take into account local values, aspirations and desires towards energy and food futures. It is believed that this approach would improve the consensus and ownership of the proposed solution, and also unlock different organizational models. Design and visualization tools, which have been introduced in the second workshop, facilitate debate, communication and social learning.

The presence of two different communities, Lincoln and Hockerton, was also seen as positive and part of the aims of ISABEL in creating a network of different local initiatives and catalyzing learning and sharing practices, which are important elements of social innovation and scaling out of community energy initiatives.

² <http://www.energylocal.co.uk/>

Figure 16. Visioning session from the second workshop at the Hockerton Housing Project, with participants using “biogas archetypes” cards to explore desirable biogas community scenarios.

Figure 17. Some results from the visioning exercise.

4.1.3 *Emerging community structure and vision*

At the moment there is not yet a defined vision and structure for the biogas community. Rather, this is an “opening up” phase, where different pathways are being explored by the different actors of the community.

From the infrastructural point of view, some of the visions that emerged during the aforementioned workshop are:

- A biomethane bottling scheme, operating between the farm and the village users (who at the moment have not access to the natural gas grid and rely on LPG for cooking)
- A community polytunnel growing scheme, producing food for the community and energetically independent.
- The installation of a micro-biogas plant operated by the local pub.

Potential sources of wastes are food waste and garden wastes from household and commercial activities, together with manure and agricultural wastes from the local farms. At the moment, no quantitative estimation of the available waste is available, as this depends mainly on the geographical boundary of the biogas community, and the sources of waste considered. Mapping of the assets, commercial activities and available waste will be one of the first activities of the action plan for the Hockerton community. Dimensions of the biogas systems therefore are still not fixed and will depend mainly on the amount of waste and business and organizational model that will emerge.

At the micro-scale (e.g. less than 1000 ton/year waste processed and 10 kWh/year of potential electricity produced) the main direct financial returns will come from digestate valorization and increased food production distributed and sold to the nearby communities. At bigger scales (e.g. using the agro-wastes and manure from farms), potential revenues from energy, such as biomethane bottling scheme, might become relevant.

In general, community biogas is seen as an entry point for longer term outcomes, creating multi-functional, sustainable ecosystems or “naturally smart places”³:

- Create a holistic, integrated model and long term vision for community-driven, service provisions (energy, food, bio-resource valorisation) and ecological restoration.
- Connect people to their place, using a process for change which enables the community to audit, study and respond to their local environment.
- Promote local or regional platforms where citizens can engage in decision-making, as well as processes through which organisations, businesses and other groups can meet together and share ideas, concerns and future plans.
- The establishment and development of a proper network of actors (at regional, national and international level to support innovation.
- Promote reflexive learning to change actors’ reference framework, beliefs, practices etc.

The benefits of a community biogas project will go beyond the financial returns of conventional energy businesses. Other factor such as increased capabilities, quality of life, health, education, relationships, ecological restoration, landscape management, increased biodiversity have been highlighted and recognised during the interaction with the community.

Different organizational models can be foreseen, including schemes which are community group led, local authority led, waste producer led (biogas system in a farm) or a partnership of between local actors and other organizations, including national support organizations or power companies. As an example, the community biogas initiative could be promoted by the existing community groups, such as Sustainable Hockerton, including the possibility of cross-subsidizing the operation of the biogas system through the feed-in-tariff incomes of the PV and wind installation; this could be an interesting model to replicate in other places.

³ <http://foundation.rocks/popupproject/naturally-smart-places/>

Hockerton has experience in raising community shares, and this is an option to finance the scheme, once the multi-benefits of initiatives will be recognised by the community actors.

Another option that emerged during the workshops, is to start small and quick, with a micro scale AD operated at the Hockerton Housing Project integrated with already existing polytunnels and aquaculture. The scheme would help to make the village and local actors more aware and improve the perception around the biogas technology, leading to easier scale out to other actors and dimensions.

One main challenge of the process will be the ability to maintain cohesion between the stakeholders during the future steps of interaction, developing a shared vision and a common purpose to motivate action and sustain participation. It will be the responsibility of ISABEL to facilitate the transition from the initial visions and desires of the community emerged in the initial workshop, into a more detailed strategy for action to be deployed in the next two years of the project.

4.2 Lincoln biogas communities

4.2.1 Description of the Community

ISABEL has started a collaboration with various organizations active in Lincoln that are responsible for the development of a new food strategy for Lincoln and the wider rural hinterland. A report was published in October 2016, which describes the main aspects of the food strategy⁴. The main stakeholders responsible for the strategy are:

- East Midlands Regional Big Food Project Board
- Public Health England, East Midlands
- City of Lincoln Council
- Lincolnshire County Council
- Rural Community Council (RCC)
- Community Lincs, a charity active developing community projects
- Peakhill Associates, renewable energy consultants
- United Lincolnshire Health Trusts
- University of Lincoln

The initial core of the food strategy and collaboration with ISABEL will be the regeneration of the covered market, a market hall located centrally in Lincoln old town. The regeneration aims to make the market a hub for wider community engagement, showcasing closed loop approaches to food production enabled by anaerobic digestion of biowastes. It is part of the engagement strategy to include other actors, such as existing market traders, charities such as the Royal Horticultural Society and the Food Share Network, community gardens organizations in Lincoln, school growing projects, health care organizations, religious organizations, and in general the various disadvantaged sectors of the society (unemployed, homeless, mentally and physically ill).

The support of ISABEL was instrumental in extending the food strategy and the community biogas approach to 4 more sites located in different location of Lincolnshire:

- Brookenby village, an ex Minister of Defence (MOD) site of around 700 inhabitants.
- Newtoft village, an ex MOD site, part of the Toft Newton civil parish with an overall population of around 500 inhabitants.

⁴ <http://eprints.lincoln.ac.uk/24922/1/Food%20Strategy%20for%20Lincoln.HART%20brochure.2016.pdf>

- Park Ward, a deprived neighbourhood in Lincoln City.
- Washingborough Academy, a school just outside Lincoln City known for innovation.

The above mentioned Ministry of Defence (MOD) sites share the same “story” of de-commissioning and current challenges in terms of lack of community assets and services.

The promoter of the Lincoln food strategy has good connections with the Lincoln City Council, including the planning department. There is already a strong network in place between various organizations running community gardening and food poverty projects. In general, it seems to be a favourable moment for ISABEL to engage with the stakeholders and assist in the formation of a biogas community initiative.

Figure 18. Location of the potential sites for biogas communities, in and surrounding the city of Lincoln.

4.2.2 Methodology of engagement and community building

The ISABEL team got in contact with the main responsible for the food strategy for Lincoln, and introduced the ISABEL project through phone calls and personal meetings. Information about ISABEL was then “cascaded” to other relevant stakeholders of the strategy. Members of a charity from Lincoln, promoters of the food strategy, participated in the second workshop organized at the Hockerton community (see section above). This workshop was followed up with further meeting and phone calls to discuss how the ISABEL concept might contribute to their vision.

The next action of engagement will be to organize a roundtable meeting with key project organizers to flesh out a co-designed action plan and timelines.

4.2.3 Emerging community structure and vision

Indoor Lincoln City Market

From an infrastructural point of view, an initial vision for the indoor city market is to host a micro AD system which would allow the recycling of food waste into vegetable growing areas hosted inside the market.

Potential sources of waste include: cooked waste from restaurants and stalls within the market and in Lincoln, and unusable/unused food from the food share network (redistribution of out of date food). Depending on the size of the system, the collection could include food waste from nearby households, restaurant and schools. Garden and green waste treatment will be integrated with existing composting facilities.

There is currently no municipal food waste collection in Lincoln, therefore the scheme could develop the opportunity for under and unemployed people to participate in the waste collection, under monetary and in-kind retributions (such as food from businesses participating in the strategy). Collection of food waste from throughout the community would raise visibility and awareness of the market project as an innovative food-growing hub.

Digestate would be re-utilised in the growing areas inside the market and the surplus would be re-distributed to the other food growing projects included in the overall Lincoln food strategy.

The covered market project aims to be a social project encouraging economic regeneration, education and training centred around food growing, cooking and retail with the aim of alleviating food poverty and growing in a sustainable manner. The market will act as a hub for the Lincoln food strategy, but also the centre of a wider movement and projects within Lincolnshire and beyond. A hub catalysing other connected projects.

The community biogas is embedded in a holistic strategy and long term vision, which encompass different themes:

- Food for health, alleviating food poverty and reskilling around basic cookery skills.
- Showcasing and training in gardening techniques which are accessible to those with very limited space, time and money.
- Gardening as therapy for (mental) health and exercise (cancer recovery).
- Commercial opportunity, improve environment for traders, make the market a place to visit.
- Community connection and focus is extremely important, especially in providing new job opportunities.
- Sustainable growing techniques including closed loop approaches.

The material connections enabled by the anaerobic biogas system would enable and be enabled by the social connections, a virtuous circle. In this sense the anaerobic digester could be seen as a “health” infrastructure, which would provide well-being and welfare benefits to the community, therefore unlocking different sources of funding beyond the classic energy and waste framework. - The project will be designed to meet the specific needs of its community and to enable new ideas to flourish from that starting point.

It is planned to create a Community Interest company in order to have the power to access to public and charity funding.

Ex MOD sites

The airfields at Brookenby and Newtoft and surrounding villages have ample supply of grass cuttings each year which they need to dispose of in maintenance operations. At the moment the council also cuts the grass in the villages around Brookenby. Land and buildings in both Brookenby and Newtoft are in plentiful supply for not only the feedstock but also for space to host the digester. Infrastructure and access are good.

All sites are deprived communities with social problems, and new biogas development are thought to provide a valuable social function.

MOD sites have community associations and community officers which would provide direct and established routes of engagement with residents and possible community champions.

5. Conclusions

Previous sections reported the community building progress in the three regions. Each emerging community has been described in terms of involved stakeholders, values and benefits, potential organizational models, infrastructural scale, material input and outputs, activities foreseen. As evident from the deliverables, each community has different characteristics.

This is an outcome itself of the ISABEL social innovation approach, which allows each community to co-create their development and responds to their priorities and local environment characteristics. It is possible to reframe a biogas system into a wider context: not only responding to top down policies such as feed in tariff addressed mainly at energy generation, but enabling local communities to re-design a biogas system in a more integrated way, delivering different outcomes. The involvement and engagement of a range of stakeholders, at different levels, can bring different definitions of value, benefits and impacts which are appropriate for their situations. Suitable organizational models will be required to deliver such new visions of business and enterprise: not only profit-maximising and resource-extractive (e.g. energy crops), but as a “form of social organisation embedded in the community, working in harmony with nature to deliver the capabilities that allow us to prosper”⁵.

The emerging biogas communities are being developed in a longer term framework:

- Considering integrated models and long term visions for community-driven provision of services (such as energy, food and bio-resource valorisation) and ecological restoration.
- Improving awareness of the local assets, resources and ecosystem by the local actors.
- Promoting local or regional platforms where citizens and organizations can meet and engage in decision-making.

The implemented stakeholder engagement and community building generally went through a progression, from an initial introduction to the main stakeholders, to a wider engagement with other local actors, starting a process of co-creation and evaluation of desirable biogas community scenarios. In each community, motivated stakeholders and local champions will support ISABEL in the next steps of community building.

From an infrastructural point of view, different scales and interventions are possible, from urban and peri-urban micro scale digesters, to manure farming based digesters and new district heating schemes. Table 1 shows the main characteristics from initial the community biogas scenarios.

⁵ http://www.cusp.ac.uk/blog/tj-growing_prosperity/

Community	Location	Biogas system	Inputs - feedstocks	Outputs - energy	Other potential outcomes
Oberschach village, Germany	Rural, village of 2000 inhabitants	District heating: linked to an existing 270 kWe biogas plant. Two other potential biogas plants could participate in the community.	Increased use of garden and food waste from households. Biowaste from landscape maintenance.	New district heating for the village. Could cover up to 50% demand. Alternatively, fuel for mobility.	Improved food and green waste management. New business model without feed-in-tariff Promote wider regional development and energy transition. Support tourism.
NEOGAL dairy cooperative, Greece	Rural, livestock breeder region	Small-large scale on-farm digesters. Dimensions depend on number of breeders co-operating in the biogas community.	Mainly manure from livestock breeders	Generation through CHP Heat for polytunnels, buildings and industrial processes.	Improved manure management and legal compliance Organic agriculture Increased co-operation between members
Leda Maria settlement, Greece	Peri-urban settlement (150 families)	Micro-scale	Mainly domestic food waste and garden waste from Leda Maria and potentially surrounding settlements and buildings	Micro-generation District and building heating	Renegotiate contracts with energy supplier Closed loop of nutrients in gardening areas Increased co-operation in the settlement and with neighbouring organizations
Prespes, Greece	Rural Protected environment (natural park)	Small-large scale, depending on number of breeders and available collected reeds.	Manure from livestock breeders Collected invasive lake plants (reeds).	Heat to district heating and productive processes.	Reduced lake eutrophication and ecosystem regeneration Protection of biodiversity Support of organic agriculture.
Hockerton, UK	Rural Initial village and co-housing of 150 inhabitants	Alternative: micro-scale (household food waste) small – large (on farm manure based)	Food and garden household waste Manure	Heat to building and polytunnel/micro-generation at micro-scale Biomethane bottling at large scale	Increased local food production and distribution. Support local economy and development. Improved manure management
Lincoln, UK	Urban, indoor city market	Micro-scale	Food waste from commercial activities and households	Heating to buildings and indoor growing areas.	Regenerate market and create hub for community activities. Support local food strategy. Educational and training opportunities
	Peri-urban and rural (4 potential sites and villages)	Micro/Small scale	Food and garden waste	Micro-generation/heat to building and district heating.	Support local food strategy. Improve social conditions. Training and job opportunities. Co-operation with educational centre

Table 1. Main characteristics from initial community biogas scenarios in the three regions.